

ANALYSIS OF THE STUDIED INDICATORS DEPENDING ON THE ACHIEVEMENT OF TARGET GLYCATED HEMOGLOBIN LEVELS BY AGE IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES AND CORONARY HEART DISEASE WITH DIFFERENT EJECTION FRACTIONS

Sh.Sh. Mukhtarova¹, R.Kh. Trigulova², M.S. Yuldasheva³, B.A. Jabbarbergenova⁴

Tashkent State Medical University^{1,3,4}

Republican Specialized Scientific–Practical Medical Center of Cardiology²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18190715>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the analysis of the target levels of glycated hemoglobin by age in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and coronary heart disease with different ejection fractions. Aim: To assess and compare indicators depending on the achievement of target glycated hemoglobin levels by age in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and coronary heart disease with different ejection fractions. A total of 130 patients with T2DM and CHD with varying LVEF were examined. The mean age was 65.6 ± 9.7 years, with disease duration of 8.8 ± 5.2 and 7.5 ± 3.6 years, respectively. The analysis showed that among T2DM patients with very high cardiovascular risk included in the study, 56.9% ($n=74$) achieved the target HbA1c level of $\leq 8\%$. HbA1c $\geq 8\%$ persisted in 43.0% ($n=74$), taking age into account. In patients with HbA1c $\geq 8\%$, the duration of CHD and T2DM was 1.5 and 1.2 times higher than in the group with HbA1c $\leq 8\%$. Meanwhile, the frequency of AF paroxysms was 4.5 times higher in the group with HbA1c $\leq 8\%$. The identified correlations demonstrated a positive association between fluctuations in HbA1c levels and the risk of macrovascular complications.*

Keywords: *coronary heart disease, Type 2 diabetes mellitus, heart failure, cardiovascular events, ejection fraction, glycated hemoglobin.*

Introduction. Diabetes mellitus is a widely recognized risk factor for a broad range of cardiovascular (CV) events, including both macrovascular and microvascular complications [1]. Current advances in diabetology emphasize the importance of a detailed study of the complex interrelationship between type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and heart failure (HF). Patients with T2DM show a higher incidence of HF and less favorable outcomes compared to individuals without diabetes [2]. T2DM exerts both direct and indirect effects on the onset of HF through associated risk factors and concomitant cardiovascular diseases. Numerous studies classify HF as a cardiovascular complication of T2DM. However, the direct impact of T2DM on the development of HF remains insufficiently studied, and most available data are based on retrospective analyses or post-hoc observations [3].

Metabolic disorders characteristic of T2DM are frequently combined with other cardiovascular risk factors. T2DM can act as a catalyst for a range of adverse changes. These include accelerated formation of atherosclerotic plaques not only in the coronary arteries but also in the systemic circulation. Endothelial damage is also observed, impairing normal vascular function.

The HbA1c level is strongly associated with heart failure (HF). However, little is known about the relationship between HbA1c variability and HF. Several studies have shown that HbA1c level is positively associated with HF in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) [7,8]. An analysis of cohort study data revealed a significant relationship between HbA1c level and the risk of developing HF.

According to the results, a decrease in mean HbA1c by one percentage point is associated with a 16% reduction in the likelihood of HF onset [5]. In parallel, recent research has identified a positive association between fluctuations in HbA1c levels and the risk of macrovascular complications [4]. Moreover, a relationship has been established between HbA1c instability and increased all-cause mortality among individuals with T2DM [6,9]. However, the association between HbA1c variability and HF remains poorly understood.

Aim: To assess and compare indicators depending on the achievement of target glycated hemoglobin levels by age in patients with T2DM and CHD with different ejection fractions.

Materials and Methods. The study included 130 patients with T2DM (WHO, 1999) and CHD (ESC), with a mean age of 65.6 ± 9.7 years. The duration of T2DM and CHD was 8.8 ± 5.2 and 7.5 ± 3.6 years, respectively. For the purpose of analyzing the dependence of studied parameters on the achievement of target HbA1c levels, patients were divided into two groups:

- **Group 1:** Target HbA1c level $\leq 8\%$ achieved (n = 74),
- **Group 2:** Target HbA1c level $\geq 8\%$ not achieved (n = 56).

Out of 92 parameters analyzed, only those with statistically significant differences were selected for discussion. Baseline therapy included: anticoagulants, antiplatelets, nitrates, beta-blockers, RAAS inhibitors, statins, empagliflozin, and GLP-1 receptor agonists. The observation period was 2 years. Statistical processing was performed using the nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis one-way analysis of variance.

Results. Comparative analysis of the frequency of clinical and anamnestic parameters in patients with CHD and T2DM depending on the achievement of target HbA1c levels showed that in Group 2, women predominated (p = 0.004), as well as individuals with a history of COVID-19 infection (p = 0.037), and patients with longer CHD duration (p = 0.025) and T2DM duration (p = 0.000) compared with Group 1. Paroxysms of AF were significantly less common (p = 0.000) than in patients who achieved HbA1c $\leq 8\%$. The frequency of AMI, stroke, PCI, and CABG had no direct relationship with HbA1c level (Table 1).

Table 1.

Comparative characteristics of the frequency of clinical and anamnestic parameters in patients with T2DM and CHD depending on the achievement of target HbA1c levels (abs/%).

Indicator	HbA1c$\leq 8\%$, n=74	HbA1c$\geq 8\%$, n=56	T	C
Average age (M \pm σ)	67,19 \pm 9,73	63,48 \pm 9,23	4,879	0,027
Women, n	48,6% (36)	62,5% (35)	8,186	0,004
Weight, kg	85,20 \pm 16,76	85,43 \pm 15,32	0,031	0,860
Height, cm	165,15 \pm 8,67	163,77 \pm 8,02	0,680	0,410
BMI, kg/m ²	31,45 \pm 6,15	31,93 \pm 4,58	1,154	0,283
History of COVID-19	48,6% (36)	58,9% (33)	4,366	0,037
Duration of diabetes, years	7,04 \pm 4,93	11,12 \pm 4,55	26,010	0,000
Duration of coronary artery disease,	6,93 \pm 3,43	8,38 \pm 3,70	5,007	0,025

years				
Atrial fibrillation/flutter	16,2% (12)	3,6% (2)	46,428	0,000
Death	0.0% (0)	1.8% (1)	1.818,	0.178
History of myocardial infarction (MI)	35,1% (26)	35,7% (20)	0,015	0,904
History of percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI)	29,7% (22)	28,6% (16)	0,066	0,798
History of coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG)	10,8% (8)	7,1% (4)	2,028	0,154
History of stroke	6,8% (5)	3,6% (2)	2,946	0,086
Stenosis of proximal LAD > 50%	12.2% (9)	7.1% (4) ^	3,798	0,051
Complex triple-vessel disease	2.7% (2)	1.8% (1)	0.479,	0.489

Note:

^ – P<0.05; ^^ – P<0.01; ^^^ – P<0.001 – intergroup statistical significance;
 * – P<0.05; ** – P<0.01; *** – P<0.001 – statistical significance in relation to Visits 1 and 2 between the groups.

The number of patients taking metformin (p=0.000), DPP-4 inhibitors (p=0.000), and insulin (p=0.000) was 1.98, 4.04, and 4.32 times higher, respectively, in the group that did not achieve the target level. At the same time, the doses of metformin (1083.97±577.95 mg) and DPP-4 inhibitors (72.50±26 mg) were higher in Group 2 compared with Group 1 (772.12±428.57 mg; t=6.395, p=0.011 and 54.17±22.44 mg; t=2.189, p=0.139, respectively). Insulin therapy showed an opposite trend: Group 1 – 35.43±18.54 vs. Group 2 – 26.87±15.78 (t=1.065, p=0.302).

Patients who achieved the target HbA1c ≤8% more often received ACE inhibitors (p=0.000), MRA antagonists (p=0.001), and loop diuretics (p=0.000). Patients in Group 2 were more frequently prescribed sartans (p=0.000), thiazide diuretics (p=0.031), and statins (p=0.000). The prescription of sacubitril/valsartan was more common during Visit 1 in Group 1 (p=0.000), but the number decreased by the second stage (p=0.06).

In patients with different HbA1c distributions, baseline and follow-up heart rate (HR) values did not differ. Systolic blood pressure (SBP) values were nearly identical: 140.35±22.62 mmHg in Group 1 vs. 139.11±17.22 mmHg in Group 2; and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) values were 85.41±11.05 vs. 84.46±7.54 mmHg, respectively. In Group 2, DBP decreased from 84.46±7.54 to 81.79±6.84 mmHg at follow-up (t=3.758, p=0.053). (Table 2).

Table 2.
Hemodynamic parameters in patients with T2DM and CHD depending on target HbA1c levels during follow-up (M±δ).

Indicators	Visit	HbA1c≤8%; n=74	HbA1c≥8%; n=56
Heart rate, bpm	1	76.07±14.46	78.45±10.67
	2	74.30±14.08	75.73±9.62
Systolic blood pressure, mmHg	1	140.35±22.62	139.11±17.22
	2	138.45±18.10	134.38±13.50
Diastolic blood pressure, mmHg	1	85.41±11.05	84.46±7.54
	2	82.50±8.98	81.79±6.84*

Changes in the analyzed glycemetic profile parameters correspond to their distribution according to HbA1c levels. The following indicators were higher in Group 2 compared with Group

1: fasting glucose – 9.94 ± 2.94 , PPG – 15.31 ± 3.85 , HbA1c – 9.23 ± 1.74 , HOMA-IR index – 7.86 ± 4.46 , and HOMA-B index – 35.47 ± 23.22 ($t=53.398$, $p=0.000$; $t=54.153$, $p=0.000$; $t=63.567$, $p=0.000$; $t=16.463$, $p=0.000$; $t=12.236$, $p=0.000$, respectively). However, insulin levels in both groups were almost identical both before ($t=0.357$, $p=0.550$) and after treatment ($t=0.008$, $p=0.927$).

Conclusion. The analysis showed that among the patients with diabetes mellitus who had a very high cardiovascular risk and were included in the study, 56.9% ($n=74$) achieved the target HbA1c $\leq 8\%$. HbA1c $\geq 8\%$ persisted in 43.0% ($n=56$), taking age into account. In patients with HbA1c $\geq 8\%$, the duration of CHD and diabetes was 1.5 and 1.2 times longer, respectively, compared with the group with HbA1c $\leq 8\%$. Meanwhile, the incidence of paroxysmal atrial fibrillation was 4.5 times higher in the group with HbA1c $\leq 8\%$. The frequency of AMI, stroke, PCI, and CABG in patient history showed no direct association with the level of HbA1c compensation. All patients received empagliflozin for cardio- and nephroprotective purposes. The number of patients and the doses of metformin and DPP-4 inhibitors were higher in the group with HbA1c $\geq 8\%$ by 1.98 and 4.04 times, respectively. Insulin therapy demonstrated the opposite trend: Group 1 – 35.43 ± 18.54 vs. Group 2 – 26.87 ± 15.78 ($t=1.065$, $p=0.302$). Patients who achieved the target HbA1c $\leq 8\%$ more frequently received ACE inhibitors ($p=0.000$), MRA antagonists ($p=0.001$), and loop diuretics ($p=0.000$). Patients with HbA1c $\geq 8\%$ were more often prescribed sartans ($p=0.000$), thiazide diuretics ($p=0.031$), and statins ($p=0.000$). ARNI therapy was more frequently prescribed at Visit 1 in Group 1 ($p=0.000$), but the number decreased by the second stage ($p=0.06$). Changes in the analyzed glycemic profile parameters correspond to their distribution according to HbA1c levels.

REFERENCES

1. Morrish, J. N., Wang, S.-L., Stevens, K. L., Fuller, H. J., & Keen, H. (2001). Mortality and causes of death in the WHO multinational study of vascular disease in diabetes. *Diabetologia*, 44, S14–S21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/pl00002934>
2. McMurray, J. J., Gerstein, H. C., Holman, R. R., & Pfeffer, M. A. (2014). Heart failure: a cardiovascular outcome in diabetes that can no longer be ignored. *The Lancet Diabetes & Endocrinology*, 2, 843–851. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-8587\(14\)70031-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-8587(14)70031-2)
3. Fitchett, D. H., Udell, J. A., & Inzucchi, S. E. (2017). Heart failure outcomes in clinical trials of glucose-lowering agents in patients with diabetes. *European Journal of Heart Failure*, 19, 43–53. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejhf.633>
4. Mo, Y., Zhou, J., Ma, X., Zhu, W., Zhang, L., Li, J., Lu, J., Hu, C., Bao, Y., & Jia, W. (2018). Hemoglobin A1c variability as an independent correlate of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease in Chinese type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes & Vascular Disease Research*, 15, 402–408. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1479164118778850>
5. Stratton, I. M., Adler, A. I., Neil, H. A., Matthews, D. R., Manley, S. E., Cull, C. A., Hadden, D., Turner, R. C., & Holman, R. R. (2000). Association of glycaemia with macrovascular and microvascular complications of type 2 diabetes (UKPDS 35): Prospective observational study. *BMJ*, 321, 405–412. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.321.7258.405>
6. Tseng, J. Y., Chen, H. H., Huang, K. C., Hsu, S. P., & Chen, C. C. (2020). Effect of mean HbA1c on the association of HbA1c variability and all-cause mortality in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism*, 22, 680–687. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dom.13951>

7. Zhao, W., Katzmarzyk, P. T., Horswell, R., Wang, Y., Johnson, J., & Hu, G. (2014). HbA1c and heart failure risk among diabetic patients. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 99, e263–e267. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2013-3325>
8. Alimova, D. A., et al. (2023). HbA1c trajectories and the course of heart failure in patients with coronary artery disease and type 2 diabetes. *Journal of Cardiorespiratory Research*, 1(2), 36–40.
9. Urmanova, Y. M., et al. (2020). Prognostic markers of adverse outcomes in coronary artery disease in patients with type 2 diabetes. *International Endocrinology Journal*, 16(2), 98–103.